

A stochastic model of the social distancing interventions to contain the Covid-19 pandemic: comparison with the Italian case

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ABSTRACT

A SIR-derived stochastic model is developed to study the spread of a virus such as the SARS-CoV-2 in a population, where relationships among individuals can be interrupted to simulate lockdowns of different intensity. Social distancing and limited hospitals capacity can also be taken into account. The properties of the model are discussed and suggestions to limit the impact of the pandemic, the number of hospitalised people and of deaths are derived. The model is also used to analyse the first and the beginning of the second wave of the contagion in Italy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing pandemic due to the SARS-CoV-2 virus is demanding a multidisciplinary approach to face the multifaceted issues that it brings to our lives, our society, our economy. Clinical and medical research are of course of primary importance to fight the disease and save human lives, but other disciplines can contribute to the effort of fighting against this fearsome enemy: Biology and Genetics in studying how the virus replicates and attacks our cells, Physics, Mathematics and Engineering in understanding how the virus spreads in the environment, in closed rooms, in a population, Human Sciences in scrutinising how it affects our society, our work, our psychology.

Within this context, a large number of studies have been conducted modelling the diffusion of the Covid-19 in complex and structured societies, covering whole regions or countries [1–9], and facing complex scenarios [10] or trying to take into account the role played by unidentified infected people [11]. These models are mostly derived from the SIR (Susceptible, Infected, Recovered) general framework, which offers a relatively simple and well established approach to epidemic models [12–14]. One of its advantages is that it is analytical, therefore analytical calculations are possible, and many mathematical tools can be exploited to prove its properties [15].

SIR models, being compartmental, fit the population into a defined number of classes or compartments [16]: while people can move across different compartments in the course of the evolution of the epidemic, this approach does not offer the possibility to differentiate individuals or subgroups of individuals, each compartment being treated homogeneously

(contrary to other approaches, see e.g. [17]). This is of course a simplification that on one hand helps keeping the model treatable analytically, but on the other hand puts some limits in the scenarios that the model could try to reproduce, and in the quantities that it could try to account for.

In order to address some of these limitations, mathematical models where interactions among individuals are described in details have also appeared, with the aim of being able to track the transmission of the virus, perform contact tracing, evaluate the effects of lockdowns [18–20]. In order to keep under control the unavoidable huge increase in complexity, these approaches are forced to significantly limit the number of simulated individuals, or restrict themselves to small populations [21]. Alternatively, completely different, and interesting, approaches exploiting artificial intelligence and machine learning have been attempted, with the aim of forecasting and limiting the diffusion of the contagion [22–24].

In this paper we propose a SIR-derived model that, instead of being treated analytically, is treated numerically. A population is made of a given number of individuals, that can be addressed independently, even though in a first approximation their properties and relationships are treated homogeneously within each compartment. Through a stochastic, Monte Carlo based approach, the evolution of the diffusion of the SARS-CoV-2 virus is simulated in the population, where options or choices such as when and how to apply lockdowns, whether or not there are limits in the medical resources to treat patients, strictness of social distancing measurements are available for simulating different scenarios. Even though the model accepts populations of arbitrary size, in its present formulation it assumes that any individual could interact, at least in principle, with any other individual of the population. This approximation is more suited for modelling the population of a city rather than a country, therefore also the size of the population should be scaled accordingly. As an example, in this paper we have set the size of the population to one million individuals, of the same order of the size of an Italian major city such as Torino. However, it is important to remark that this model does not aim to describe faithfully how the epidemics evolve in Torino or in any other specific city. It rather aims to provide tools useful to establish the effects of choices, decisions and parameters to critical quantities such as number of deaths, number of infected people, occupancy of hospitals and intensive therapies. It is therefore a tool to simulate scenarios and understand different strategies to fight against the epidemics.

II. MODEL

The model is SIR-derived, and is based on Monte Carlo simulations of a population obeying a given set of rules and relationships among its members that are described in the following section.

II.1. Description

The population is described as a set of N individuals or persons. Each person maintains relationships with a number of other individuals, accordingly to the following scheme:

- **family:** an *average* number of f persons constitutes the family group of each individual; the family relationship is mutual, i.e. if person b is a member of the family of person a , then also a is a member of the family of b . However, families are not necessarily closed groups as f is only the average number of persons belonging to the same family; therefore, the family group of person a could be made of more people than that of person b , therefore a would have contacts external to those that b has. A real-life example could be a couple where the parents of one of the spouses maintain contacts only with their son or daughter but not with his or her spouse. The relationships in a family group cannot be broken, the case of an absolute segregation of an individual being trivial and not taken into account in the simulations.
- **work:** an *average* number of w persons constitutes the work group of each individual, i.e. the number of people this individual spends a significant amount of time with, while working. Even though there are cases where this relationship is mutual (e.g. two persons sharing the same office), as in the case of the family group, the work group is not considered mutual in this model, as in many other cases the relationship is asymmetrical (a shop keeper has in his / her work group the customers, but each customer hardly exchanges time with more than one or two shop keepers in a given time unit).
- **friends:** an *average* number of r persons constitutes a friends group of each individual, i.e. a set of acquaintances the person spends, occasionally, some time with. This group is equivalent to the work group, except that it can be easier to suspend the interactions

with the friends group than with the work group (during a partial lockdown, bars, pubs, cinemas etc. may be closed, but workplaces can still be open).

- **other:** an *average* number of o persons constitutes a other group of each individual, i.e. a set of persons that he / she meets randomly and occasionally, usually for a relatively short period of time (e.g. on a bus, at the supermarket, etc.). This group is again equivalent to the friends and work groups, and is kept separated only because it can constitute a different level of confinement during a partial lockdown.

f , w , r and o are average group sizes; for each person, the actual groups size is calculated using a gaussian distribution, having those average values and 1.7, 10, 20 and 50 as standard deviations respectively. This accounts for the relatively large differences among individuals in the numerosness of their contacts, with persons having only a bunch of friends and little social interactions, and others who frequently go out with very large companies and frequent busy entertainment places.

At time $t_0 = 0$, an initial number of people I_0 is infected. For each individual, a counter i identifies whether he / she is infected or not. These people are taken randomly from the entire population. Then, time t is let increase, iteratively. At each iteration, the following steps are executed:

1. the time t is increased by 1 unit.
2. all persons in N are iterated; for each person, if $i > 0$, i.e. the person is infected, then the counter i is increased by 1 unit.
3. for each person in N , all the individuals of the family, work, friends and other groups are considered; if the person is infected, he /she has a probability s of infecting any of the individuals belonging to those groups (unless confinement rules are applied, see later). If the infection is propagated, the counter i associated to the person being infected increases by one unity.
4. for each person in N , a threshold i_{as} is defined such that if $i < i_{as}$ then the person is considered asymptomatic (but contagious).
5. for each person in N , a threshold i_{hos} is defined such that if $i_{as} \leq i < i_{hos}$ then the person is considered having symptoms that are sufficiently severe to require hospital-

isation. In this case, the person is isolated, i.e. he / she no longer has any contacts with his / her family, work, friends or group members.

6. for each person in N , a threshold i_{dt} is defined such that if $i_{hos} \leq i < i_{dt}$ then the health conditions of that person have become so serious that a move to intensive therapy is required. Also in this case, the person is fully isolated, and cannot spread the infection to anyone else. Therefore, i_{hos} is a threshold dividing people that are admitted in hospitals but do not need intensive therapy ($i < i_{hos}$) from those whose conditions are severe enough to require intensive therapy ($i \geq i_{hos}$).
7. if $i \geq i_{dt}$ then the person dies of the consequences of the disease.
8. at any iteration, an infected person ($i > 0$) has a probability d of dying because of sudden worsening of his / her health conditions, independent on the value of i . This is of course a simplification, that is partially mitigated by the previous item, which forces an infected person's death once the "disease index" i has grown too much ($i \geq i_{dt}$).
9. for each person in N , if he / she is infected and with $i < i_{dt}$, a probability h is defined allowing for healing and complete recovery from the disease. From that moment on, the person can restore full contacts with the other individuals of the family, work, friends and other groups, but is not infected ($i = 0$), cannot spread the infection, and is considered immune at least at short term, i.e. for the duration of the simulation, therefore he / she cannot become infected a second time.

The simulation ends when there are no longer infected people: in this condition, all people that have been infected in the course of time are either healed or dead. Some people have never been infected, and will never be in the course of the simulation, since the disease has already disappeared (the number of infected people has reduced to zero). A scheme in pseudo-code resuming the above steps is reported in Figure 1.

The mechanism implemented by the counter i associated to each person, although crude, offers a few immediate advantages. First of all its value increases with time (indeed, it can suddenly reduce to zero when a person heals, see step 9 discussed above, but then it will never increase any more as the person is marked as immune), accounting in a simple way the evolution of the disease in the person (from no symptoms to the need of medical care to intensive therapy to, eventually, death if recovery does not come first). Then, it easily

```

set  $t = 0$ 
repeat:
   $t++$ 
  for each person  $p$  in  $N$ :
    if  $i > 0$ :
       $i++$  ■
      iterate over  $p$ 's contacts (which depend on confinement):
        if  $i < i_{as}$  ( $p$  is asymptomatic):
          increase their index  $i$  by 1 with probability  $s \cdot m$  ■
    if  $i \geq i_{as}$ :
       $p$  is hospitalised (intensive therapy if  $i \geq i_{hos}$ )
       $i += i_{untr}$  if  $p$  cannot be admitted in hospitals ■
    if  $i \geq i_{dt}$ :
       $p$  dies ●
    if  $i > 0$ :
       $p$  dies of sudden complications with a probability  $d$  ●
      if not yet dead,  $p$  heals spontaneously with a probability  $h$  ●
  count how many living people are infected (their  $i > 0$ )
  if they are 0:
    end simulation

```

FIG. 1. Scheme in pseudo-code summarising the time evolution of the contagion. Squares indicate steps where the index i is incremented (blue squares: i refers to the person p currently considered; red square: i refers to the persons belonging to p 's contacts). Circles indicate steps where the person p exits the simulation (black circles: p dies; green circle: p heals).

accounts for different “viral charges”: a person having lots of contacts and interactions with many other individuals can receive the infection from multiple sources, therefore augmenting the viral charge he / she is submitted to. This means that i increases by more than one unit at some time iterations (as each transmission from an infected individual implies an increase of i by one, see step 2 above), implying that that person will see a faster aggravation of his / her health conditions with respect to persons having fewer social contacts. Moreover, as i_{dt} remains the same, that same person has less time for the probability h to cause recovery, increasing again the risk of death. Of course, this mechanism is nonetheless too crude to take into account several other effects, such as comorbidity, age, genetics, etc.

Table I summarises the parameters of the model and their values used in the simulations.

In order to try to keep the spreading of the infection under control, confinement rules can be activated as time t elapses. The following schemes apply:

TABLE I. Parameters and their values used in the simulations.

Parameter	Value	Meaning
N	$1 \cdot 10^6$	Population size
f	5	Average family group size
w	20	Average work group size
r	30	Average friends group size
o	50	Average other group size
I_0	10	Initial number of infected people
i	≥ 0	Counter reporting the evolution of the disease for each individual
s	≥ 0	Probability of an infected person to spread the infection to someone else
i_{as}	$1/3 i_{dt}$	Threshold between asymptomatic and hospitalised persons
i_{hos}	$2/3 i_{dt}$	Threshold between hospitalised persons and those in intensive therapy
i_{dt}	≥ 0	Threshold at which an infected person dies
d	≥ 0	Probability of a person to die independent on value of i
h	≥ 0	Probability of an infected person to heal
t_{up}	≥ 0	Threshold of hospitalised people above which a <i>work confinement</i> is applied
t_{down}	≥ 0	Threshold below which <i>no confinement</i> is applied, but with social distancing
m	$[0; 1]$	Parameter multiplying s and indicating the effectiveness of social distancing
H_{max}	≥ 0	Maximum hospitals capacity
i_{untr}	≥ 0	Increased worsening of health conditions i of untreated people

- **no confinement:** people are never confined, except for those whose index i exceeds i_{as} who are hospitalised or even in intensive therapy (and therefore isolated).
- **other confinement:** mild confinement, preventing people from meeting even occasionally with individuals belonging to their other group. Isolation of the hospitalised people persists.
- **friends confinement:** confinement involving all social activities of leisure (bars, pubs, restaurants, gyms, etc.), preventing people from meeting even occasionally with individuals belonging to their other and friends groups. Isolation of the hospitalised

people persists.

- **work confinement:** confinement implying the closure of working activities (in this model there is no distinction between activities that cannot be stopped by any means and the others), preventing people from meeting even occasionally with individuals belonging to their other, friends and work groups. Indeed, people can have social interactions only with individuals belonging to their family group. This confinement is approximately equivalent to that applied in Italy and in other countries during the full lockdown period. Isolation of the hospitalised people persists.
- **family confinement:** confinement implying full isolation even from family members. It is equivalent to the isolation that hospitalised people have. A confinement of such a kind is extremely severe (no one can interact with no one else), impractical, trivial (since there is no way to spread the disease, the epidemic spontaneously fades out after a certain time), and will not be considered here.
- **threshold confinement:** in this condition, *no confinement* is initially taking place, but when the number of hospitalised people (including those in intensive therapy) increases beyond a certain threshold t_{up} , then a *work confinement* is applied. This is similar to what has been done in Italy and in other countries during the so-called phase 1 of the lockdown. Then, when the number of hospitalised people decreases below another threshold t_{down} , *no confinement* is again applied (similar to the so-called phase 2 of the lockdown in many countries), but social distancing is mandatory. Social distancing is taken into account with a parameter $m \in [0; 1]$ that multiplies s (see Table I and step 3 of the algorithm) where $m = 1$ means that social distancing is not effective at all, and $m = 0$ means that it is so effective that infected people, even if they spend a lot of time with others, will never spread the disease to them.

Additionally, the availability of limited healthcare resources (e.g. limited places in hospitals and intensive therapies) is taken into account by imposing a maximum number of people H_{max} that can be hospitalised at any instant of time. If a subject needing hospitalisation (i.e. whose $i \geq i_{as}$) does not find any place in hospitals, then his / her health conditions worsen faster than those of treated people; this mechanism is implemented in step 2 of the algorithm by incrementing i by $1 + i_{untr}$ (with $i_{untr} \geq 0$). A person in this condition is

treated, in the present model, as if he / she were completely isolated, so that he / she cannot spread the disease, in spite of not being admitted in a hospital. It is however possible to improve the model by mitigating this assumption.

Finally, the following definitions and relationships hold:

- **infected** person: a person whose index $i > 0$.
- **asymptomatic** person: a person whose index $0 < i < i_{as}$. As these people are infected but they do not know it, they can spread the disease as they keep their usual social contacts (unless forms of confinement are imposed).
- **symptomatic** person: a person whose index $i_{as} \leq i < i_{hos}$; this person is at hospitals or in any case under strict isolation, and cannot contribute in spreading the disease.
- **intensive therapy** person: a person whose index $i_{hos} \leq i < i_{dt}$.
- **hospitalised** person: a person either *symptomatic* or in *intensive therapy*. Therefore, the number of *hospitalised* persons is equal to the number of persons *symptomatic* plus the number of those in *intensive therapy*.
- **total hospitalised**: the total number of persons that have been hospitalised in the course of time (and that have either recovered or are dead at the end of the simulation).
- **total infected**: the total number of persons that have been infected in the course of time (and that have either recovered or are dead at the end of the simulation).
- **daily hospitalised**: new people entering in hospitals at any instant t of time of the simulation, i.e. whose i passes through i_{as} .
- **daily intensive therapy**: new people entering in intensive therapy at any instant t of time of the simulation, i.e. whose i passes through i_{hos} .
- **dead** person: a person whose index i has exceeded i_{dt} or that has dead for sudden worsening of his / her health conditions.

II.2. Properties

Figure 2 shows an example of a typical set of simulated curves. The two panels in each row represent the same data, in linear (Figure 2(a, c)) and logarithmic (Figure 2(b, d)) scales along the vertical axis, for best viewing features that occur at different scales. No confinement has been applied in the first example (panels a, b), i.e. the infection is left spreading uncontested, while threshold confinement is applied in the second example (panels c, d). Both examples are simulated starting from the same population, with the parameters indicated in Figure 2. Several features of the model appear by examining the curves of Figure 2(a, b). The typical characteristics of SIR-like models is evident, with curves representing total (integrated) quantities having a sigmoidal shape (total number of infected, healed or dead people), and curves representing instantaneous quantities having a more or less symmetrical bell shape (infected, asymptomatic, hospitalised and admitted in intensive therapy people). The infection starts spreading unnoticed, as all the infected people are also asymptomatic. Only after a certain time hospitalisation (and deaths) begins. When hospitalised people reach a value that is supposed to alarm the health and political authorities, a significant delay with respect to the beginning of the epidemics has already passed, and the number of infected people is already quite elevated. In the case represented in Figure 2(a,b) no confinement is imposed, so the virus spreads exponentially until a very large number of people has been infected. Indeed, the epidemic slows down only because almost the whole population has been infected, but those that have healed are immune to a new contagion (the possibility that immunity disappears after a certain period of time is not currently implemented in the model, but can be taken into account as an improvement). In this way, the curve of infected people starts decreasing, but people hospitalised or admitted in intensive therapy follow the decline only after a certain amount of time, representative of the time constant of the disease to evolve into a healing or a death. All these characteristics are typical of a SIR-like model, as this model is also expected to be.

Other additional features appear when the threshold confinement is applied (Figure 2(c, d)). Its effect is, obviously, to reduce the number of infected people (and therefore all the other quantities that derive from it). However, as the total number of infected and healed people stabilises and the number of people who are infected, asymptomatic, hospitalised and admitted to intensive therapy goes down, at a certain point the threshold t_{down} will be

FIG. 2. Representative curves of the time evolution of the simulated parameters. The same data are represented in each row, in linear (a, c) and logarithmic (b, d) scale along the vertical axis. The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $s = 0.03$, $t_{up} = 500$, $t_{down} = 50$, $m = 1.0$, H_{max} unlimited, $i_{untr} = 0$; no confinement (a, b) and threshold confinement (c, d) with $m = 1$.

reached (the number of people hospitalised for Covid-19 goes below that threshold), and the health or political authorities will relax the confinement: it is the so-called “phase 2”. If adequate social distancing measurements are not taken (in Figure 2(c,d) the coefficient m has been set to 1, indicating that there is no constraint to a free spread s of the virus after release of the confinement restrictions), all the simulated quantities will start increasing again, in successive “waves” determined by the alternating lockdown and “free” periods as hospitals populate and empty. The process goes on as long as there are people that can be infected, almost as in the “no confinement” scenario.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.1. Role of confinement

Figure 3 reports several parameters calculated for the different confinement scenarios as a function of the spread coefficient s . The chosen parameters are the total number of infected people (Figure 3(a)), the total number of deaths (Figure 3(b)), the total number of hospitalised people (Figure 3(c)) and the total number of people that have been admitted in intensive therapy (Figure 3(d)). Some of these quantities are not experimentally accessible (such as the total number of infected people, which includes also those that are positive to Covid-19 but have not been screened or detected), while others have been tracked by the sanitary and political authorities. The city of Torino, Italy, at the end of September 2020 (therefore before the beginning of the second wave of the epidemic), is used as a reference. For a value of the spread coefficient $s = 0.020$, deaths and hospitalised people are comparable to those experimentally observed [25]. Even if the present model does not aim to accurately reproduce the numbers of a specific city or region, this comparison helps picking a reasonable value for s , namely 0.020.

Perusal of Figure 3 gives some clear indications on the role of the spread coefficient s and of confinement scenarios. As expected, the work confinement, where people remain in contact only with their family members, is extremely effective at preventing the spread of the epidemic, except for very high values of s , where nothing but individual confinement of every person can limit the contagion. Of course, the work confinement, applied from the very beginning, is unrealistic, as it would presume that the authorities know the existence (and the dangers) of the epidemic before it has even started spreading. Any relaxation of the confinement scenario causes an immediate worsening of all the parameters, which can be extremely dramatic (e.g. the virus quickly reaches practically the whole population, while the number of deaths explodes to terrifying levels).

Interestingly, the threshold confinement turns out to potentially be a very effective means of taking the epidemic under control. Even though the spread of the virus starts without any constraints, the obligation to follow a rigid confinement (work confinement) as soon as the number of hospitalised people goes beyond a certain threshold helps keeping all the parameters to relatively low levels.

FIG. 3. Effect of spread coefficient s on total number of infected people (a), total number of deaths (b), total number of hospitalised people (c) and total number of people in intensive therapy (d) for different confinement scenarios. The dashed vertical line placed at $s = 0.020$ crosses the line of the threshold confinement identifying a situation comparable with the one in the city of Torino, Italy, at the end of September 2020 [25]. The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $t_{up} = 500$, $t_{down} = 50$, $m = 0.1$, H_{max} unlimited, $i_{untr} = 0$.

To help understanding how important it is to anticipate as much as possible the “work confinement” in a threshold confinement scenario, Figure 4(a) shows the time evolution of some relevant quantities, such as the total number of infected people, the number of hospitalised people and the number of deaths. In the simulation described in Figure 4(a), a value of $t_{up} = 500$ is considered, meaning that the health or political authorities decide for a lockdown when 500 people are in hospitals because of Covid-19. As the vertical dashed line clearly shows, however, at that point the number of people that have already been infected is extremely large (please note that in Figure 4(a) the vertical scale is logarithmic). For this reason, both the number of hospitalised people and the total number of deaths will keep on increasing for a while, for a factor of almost 10, before the effects of the confinement will

FIG. 4. (a) Time evolution of some relevant quantities (total infected people: black line; hospitalised people: red line; deaths: green line) for the threshold confinement scenario. The horizontal dashed line indicates the threshold used for the confinement ($t_{up} = 500$). The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $s = 0.02$, $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $t_{down} = 50$, $m = 0.1$, H_{max} unlimited, $i_{untr} = 0$. (b) Some relevant quantities (infected people: black line; total infected people: red line; deaths: green line; hospitalised people: blue line; people admitted in intensive therapy: cyan line) as a function of the threshold used for confinement in a “threshold confinement” scenario. The same parameters as in panel (a) have been used except that t_{up} is now varying.

appear.

It is therefore extremely important to reduce t_{up} as much as possible, as shown in Figure 4(b). All the relevant quantities (e.g. number of infected people, total number of infected people, deaths, hospitalised people, people admitted in intensive therapy) decrease linearly when t_{up} is decreased (please note again that the vertical scale in Figure 4(b) is logarithmic). Therefore, anticipating the lockdown (the “work confinement”) when t_{up} is only 200 or 100 with respect to 500 will mean reducing the number of deaths to 48% or 27% respectively. Conversely, waiting longer before activating a lockdown has devastating effects.

Early activation of a lockdown has positive effects also on the emergency departments of hospitals, as can be seen in Figure 5. In panel (a), the number of people who are admitted in hospitals for each time unit (that, for convenience, we will call a “day” until a calibration of the time unit is provided in Section IV.2) is plotted as a function of time, for three values of the confinement threshold t_{up} . The three dashed vertical lines indicate the instants of time for which the lockdown has been instantiated by health or political authorities. These

FIG. 5. (a) Time evolution of the number of people who are admitted in each time unit in hospitals (presumably through emergency departments), for three different confinement threshold values ($t_{up} = 500, 200, 100$ respectively for green, red and blue symbols). The vertical dashed lines represent the instant of times at which the lockdown is set, from left to right, respectively for $t_{up} = 100, 200, 500$. (b) Peak number of hospitalised people admitted in one time unit as a function of t_{up} . The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $s = 0.02$, $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $t_{down} = 50$, $m = 0.1$, H_{max} unlimited, $i_{untr} = 0$.

instants of time are easily identified as those when the number of hospitalised people exceeds for the first time the chosen threshold t_{up} . At the beginning of the simulation, the disease spreads across the population in a similar way in all cases (statistically, given the stochastic nature of the model), as no confinement has been imposed yet. Higher values for t_{up} result in a confinement taking place slightly later in time (the three dashed vertical lines in Figure 5 appear from left to right in increasing order of t_{up} values). Even though at those instants of time the number of new people accessing the emergency departments of hospitals may seem low (and not significantly dependent on t_{up}), it will significantly increase shortly after, in spite of the “work confinement” already being active, because, as we discussed earlier, at that time already a significant amount of the population would have been exposed to the virus. The peak of new people daily admitted in hospitals will also strongly depend on t_{up} because anticipating the lockdown as early as possible reduces the spread of the virus before its effects are reflected into hospitals. Therefore, a confinement as anticipated as possible has also the expected effect of keeping low the stress on the emergency departments of hospitals.

III.2. Role of social distancing

Once the lockdown is released and the so-called phase 2 begins, social distancing must be observed, through keeping mutual distancing among people, wearing face masks, and any number of actions that political and health authorities dictate [26, 27]. In the model, the cumulative effect of social distancing is taken into account by the parameter m , that multiplies the spread parameter s . Therefore, if $m = 1.0$ social distancing is completely ineffective, whereas if $m = 0.0$ it reduces the effective spread to zero, therefore being equivalent to the strictest confinement but without restraining the movement and the activities of people. Values in the interval $[0; 1]$ represent more realistic situations, also keeping in mind that face masks have been proven to be extremely effective in reducing the risks of spreading the virus [28].

The effect of social distancing through the parameter m is described in Figure 6. Panels (a) and (b) represent the total number of infected people and of deaths respectively, for the case where $s = 0.02$ or 0.03 and $t_{up} = 200$, if m is varied from 0.0 to 1.0 . It can be clearly seen that both quantities remain constant (at the low values compatible with the parameters that have been chosen for the lockdown conditions) until a certain value of m , above which they start growing quite rapidly. The value of m at which this change of behaviour is detected is such that the product $s \cdot m$ is constant; this product could be interpreted as an equivalent of the R_t parameter [29]: if $s \cdot m$ is below a certain threshold, the epidemic is not able to sustain itself, and will fade out, whereas if it is above that threshold, then it will spread uncontrolled, more or less rapidly.

The huge jump in the number of total infected people or deaths reported in Figure 6, however, must be perused to identify its sources. Figure 6(c) shows, as a function of time, what happens to the number of deaths (the number of total infected people has a similar behaviour) as a function of time, for the scenario where $s = 200$ and $t_{up} = 500$ (threshold confinement), in the two cases immediately before ($m = 0.6$) and immediately after ($m = 0.7$) the jump of Figure 6(a,b). While for $m = 0.6$ (the blue curve) the number of deaths grows up and reaches a stable state, at which the epidemic stops because the contagion fades out, the scenario for $m = 0.7$ (black curve) is richer. At the beginning, the two (black and blue) curves are superimposed (apart from small fluctuations due to the stochastic nature of the model), because the epidemic starts uncontrolled (under the same conditions)

FIG. 6. Evolution of the total infected people (a) and number of deaths (b) as a function of the social distancing coefficient m for the threshold confinement scenario. The dashed lines represent the locus where the product $m \cdot s$ is constant. The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $t_{down} = 50$, H_{max} unlimited, $i_{untr} = 0$. Time evolution of the number of deaths (c) and of the number of hospitalised people (d) for $s = 0.02$, $t_{up} = 500$ and $m = 0.7$ (black curves) and $m = 0.6$ (blue curves). In the insets, the same curves are represented, magnified for shorter simulation times.

until t_{up} is reached and lockdown is applied. When things have sufficiently improved and the number of hospitalised people falls below t_{down} , the two curves separate. The blue one ($m = 0.6$) reaches a stable state because the product $s \cdot m$ is small enough to prevent a self-sustainment of the epidemic. Conversely, the black one ($m = 0.7$) starts increasing again, marking the “second wave” of the contagion. The model assumes that a new lockdown will take place when the number of hospitalised people exceeds t_{up} and it will be removed when it goes below t_{down} , therefore triggering that behaviour clearly visible in Figure 6(c) and (d) (for the number of hospitalised people), that repeats itself almost identically until the total number of infected people reaches the level where almost no one, in the surviving population, remains unaffected by the virus. The epidemic eventually extinguishes because

the virus, practically, has no remaining hosts to infect. However, hopefully political and health authorities will take proper actions to prevent such a continuous bouncing from a lockdown to a “phase 2” state. Once the second wave come, which in any case is responsible for a significant increase of the number of deaths ($\approx 50\%$ in our scenario), hopefully the trend will be interrupted by adequate confinement measurements that will stop further bouncing. Therefore, the huge jump of Figure 6(a,b) must not be interpreted literally, but as a sign that the social distancing measurements that have been taken (therefore, the value of m) are not sufficient to guarantee that a second wave of contagion will not come; and several additional ones, if proper measures to reduce the value of m are not implemented.

III.3. Role of adequate hospitals capacity

As the resources available for taking care of the population are not infinite, it is extremely important to keep track of the number of people requiring medical assistance in hospitals, as the number of beds is limited. A city like Torino has approximately 4000 beds for acute hospitalisation [31], only a fraction of which is available to Covid-19 patients. Any political or health authority facing an emergency due to the epidemic must take this limited hospitals capacity into account.

The model allows to set a limit H_{max} to the number of people that can be admitted into hospitals at any instant of time for Covid-19 pathologies. When this limit is passed, those who cannot be admitted are subjected to an evolution of the disease that can be worse than those receiving proper medical care in hospitals. This difference is accounted by the parameter i_{untr} , that when equal to zero indicates that patients not admitted in hospitals have the same evolution of the disease as if they had been hospitalised. Any value > 0 indicates that the disease evolves more rapidly, and possibly with fatal prognosis, than for hospitalised patients.

Figure 7(a) shows a simulated scenario where $H_{max} = 1000$ is almost $\frac{2}{3}$ of the peak of people that would require hospitalisation, meaning that at the peak request to admit people into hospitals, approximately one over three would not find a bed. When $i_{untr} = 0$ (black curves), that does not make any difference in fact, since it is assumed that the evolution of the disease is unchanged. The number of deaths in this scenario stabilises to a certain value, that increases once i_{untr} becomes larger (1 or 2, in the simulated cases). It is important

FIG. 7. (a) Number of hospitalised people (continuous lines) and number of deaths (dashed lines) as a function of time, for different values of i_{untr} . The following parameters have been used for the simulation: $i_{dt} = 500$, $d = 0.0001$, $h = 0.01$, $t_{up} = 200$, $t_{down} = 50$, $m = 0.5$, $H_{max} = 1000$. (b) Number of deaths as a function of i_{untr} for three different values of H_{max} .

to remark that i_{untr} somewhat crudely tries to take into account that inadequate medical care performed at home instead of in hospitals can make the disease worse. Anyway, the patients that would have required hospitalisation and that have remained at home for lack of available resources are still under strict confinement, meaning that they do not have the opportunity to infect other people, in spite of being at their home. Of course this is a rather ideal situation, the real case being probably worse. The three peaks of hospitalised people in Figure 7(a) are overlapping, besides some small fluctuations due to the stochastic nature of the model, as they depend only on what has happened before the confinement threshold, fixed at an occupancy of hospitals t_{up} of 200 people, whereas the number of deaths increases as i_{untr} increases.

This situation is better depicted in Figure 7(b), where the number of deaths is plotted as a function of i_{untr} for three values of H_{max} . Very low values of this parameter, e.g. $H_{max} = 200$, which could be typical of a pre-epidemics condition where hospitals and intensive therapies are not properly equipped for the epidemic about to soar, will result in number of deaths that increase very rapidly with i_{untr} . Even if the exact value that i_{untr} could assume is difficult to assess, nonetheless Figure 7(b) clearly shows the importance that the health system is prepared with adequate resources to face the peak of people requiring medical assistance, otherwise the number of deaths would dramatically increase. For the same reason, as discussed for Figures 4 and 5, it is extremely important that the arising of a wave of

contagion is detected as early as possible, to keep the peak of hospitalised people as low as possible.

IV. COVID-19: THE ITALIAN CASE

IV.1. The first wave of the epidemic in Italy

Even if the model is not supposed to scale to a population covering a whole State or, probably, a Region, it is nonetheless interesting to try to compare some experimental data with the numerical results. Numerous data are available for Italy, either at a national level [32] and with a regional granularity [33].

Figure 8 shows a summary of the data available for the different Italian Regions [33], for what concerns the first wave of the epidemic (only data up to September 30th are therefore considered). For each Region (a square data point in the graph of Figure 8), two quantities have been taken into account. The first is the number of people that were already hospitalised at the date of the beginning of the lockdown (March 9th for the whole country); this number is then normalised to the peak of hospitalised people in each region, thus giving rise to the abscissa of the graph in Figure 8. The second quantity is the number of deaths in each Region, normalised by total population of that Region. The data points in Figure 8 can be gathered into three groups: the one highlighted with the red shade consists of regions that experienced a relatively high number of deaths with respect to the total population; the one highlighted in green, conversely, consists of Regions with substantially low number of deaths normalised to the total population; finally, the one with a white background lies in between. In the right part of Figure 8, each Region is coloured with the shade used to highlight its corresponding data point in the graph, showing that the groups formed by the Regions are geographically well-defined.

Of course the proposed model does not strictly apply at a national level, and at a Regional one is already quite stretched, however it is possible to try to place some simulated data points (the triangles in Figure 8) in the three groups collecting the Italian Regions. In order to reproduce the different experimental values of the reduced hospitalised people at lockdown and normalised number of deaths, the model offers two parameters to play with: the threshold confinement t_{up} , and the spread of the contagion s . As only the first wave

FIG. 8. Squares: number of deaths occurred in the Italian Regions, normalised to the total population of the corresponding Region, as a function of the number of people who were hospitalised at the date of the lockdown (March 9th, 2020) normalised to the peak number of people who have been hospitalised. Triangles: data points obtained from simulations with varying s (colour scale), and t_{up} between 10 and 500. For all the simulations, $m = 0.1$ has been considered. In the right panel, a map of Italy is reported, where the Regions are coloured with the same shade used to highlight data points in the graph.

of the contagion is of interest at this point, the role of social distancing can be ruled out: therefore, the parameter m has been set equal to 0.1 for all the simulations appearing in Figure 8. Higher values of t_{up} correspond to higher values of the abscissa of the graph, and also to a higher number of deaths. However, it is necessary to change s slightly to scatter the simulated points in the three groups where the experimental ones gather. In particular, the value used for s in the different simulations is coded by the colour with which the corresponding triangular symbol is plotted in Figure 8.

It is therefore possible to describe different scenarios for the Region belonging to different groups. The Regions of the red group are characterised by a relatively higher number of deaths. Overall, this is due either to the fact that the number of hospitalised people at the date of the lockdown was already significant (the lockdown started at the same date for the whole country, but for those Regions it was already late), or to the fact that even if the hospitals were still relatively free, the virus could spread more efficiently than elsewhere. The simulations assume that once an individual is identified as affected by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, then he/she cannot infect anyone else until he/she recovers or dies, but

this is not necessarily the case in reality, especially in those Regions where aged people have been severely hit by the disease when infected people have been admitted in the protected residences often occupied by particularly old and fragile persons.

Conversely, for the Regions of the green group the spread coefficient s is on average lower. There can be differences across a whole country due not to the virus itself, but to different habits or behaviours of populations living in different areas and climates. It must also be noted that the regions in the red group are among the most densely populated in Italy, which could also account for a higher spread parameter s .

IV.2. The second wave of the epidemic in Italy

At the time of writing this paper (October 2020), the second wave of the epidemic in Italy is only at the beginning. However, the model allows to discuss the role of some of its parameters in affecting the time between the first and second wave. Figure 9 shows the role of the spread parameter s , of the confinement threshold t_{up} and of the social distancing coefficient m on the time elapsing between the first and the second peak of hospitalised people. Of course, as noted in Figure 6, only relevant values of m are taken for the given s and t_{up} pairs, i.e. those giving rise to the subsequent waves of the contagion.

Perusal of Figure 9 shows that the time period between the first and the second peak of hospitalised people (and therefore the first and the second wave of the contagion) increases as the social distancing coefficient m decreases. This means that when the social distancing measures are weaker, new waves of the contagion come quicker. Similarly, if the contagion spreads less efficiently (lower values of s), the time period becomes longer. Conversely, the confinement threshold t_{up} acts making the period longer if it is higher: in fact, higher t_{up} means higher numbers of hospitalised people (which, as we discussed previously, must be avoided) and more time to recover to a global condition allowing for releasing the lockdown restrictions, turning out in longer times between the first and second wave of the epidemic. In general, all this applies also to the subsequent waves, if any.

Even if the model performs iterations over a time base that is arbitrary (see the arbitrary units in Figure 9), it is still possible to try to calibrate it by comparing some simulated features with experimental data. Figure 10 shows the first peak of hospitalised people as obtained from the official data on the epidemic in Italy [32]. The first peak of hospitalised

FIG. 9. Time elapsing between the first and the second peak of hospitalised people, for different values of s , t_{up} and m .

people occurred on April 5th, 2020. Its full width half maximum (FWHM) is equal to 50 days. It is then possible to compare this FWHM with that of the peaks obtained with the simulations, for values of the parameters that could be representative of the Italian situation. Representative values, obtained by averaging the simulated curves for the different values of m , are reported in Table II

As it turns out, the FWHM of the first peak of hospitalised people depends slightly on the simulation parameters. As the exact values of these parameters, more effectively representing the global Italian situation, are not known, some uncertainty is associated to the calibration of the time base of the simulations. By dividing the FWHM of Table II with the experimental one (50 days, see Figure 10), the last column of Table II is obtained, expressed in a.u. / day. Finally, the period between the first and the second wave of the contagion, according to Figure 9, could correspond to $\approx 200 - 300$ days, i.e. 7 - 10 months. As the first hospitalisation peak in Italy occurred on April 5th, 2020, the second

FIG. 10. Time evolution of the peak of hospitalised people for the first wave of the contagion in Italy.

TABLE II. Full width half maximum of the first peak of hospitalised people for different simulation parameters, and corresponding calibration of the simulation time base. The values are obtained by averaging curves over different values of m .

spread s	confinement threshold t_{up}	average FWHM (a.u.)	time base calibration (a.u. / day)
0.02	200	512	10.2
0.02	500	458	9.2
0.03	200	433	8.7

hospitalisation peak should fall within the beginning of November 2020 and the beginning of February 2021, with December 2020 and January 2021 being the most probable months. It is extremely important to point out that the simulations have been performed for a population much more homogeneous than that of a whole country like Italy, and that the

simulations consider that the social distancing measures, taken after the t_{down} threshold has been passed, are applied continuously and uniformly until t_{up} is passed again, giving rise to a new threshold confinement. These conditions may not be rigorously true in any real case.

V. DEVELOPMENT AND EXPANSION

In spite of its simplicity, the model allows several further developments and expansions, that are briefly discussed here. The fact that individual people can be addressed in the model means that many properties that so far have been considered uniform can be adapted to single persons or to groups of people. For example, an age or the membership to an age group could be attributed to each person: “young” people could be more prone to be exposed to the virus (increased number of contacts, reduced m value), having a more dynamic social life, whereas “aged” people could be more fragile (lower i_{dt} , increased d), as comorbidity has been found to be a major source of complications leading to death [30].

As another example, social distancing, instead of being applied uniformly through the whole population, could be relaxed ($m = 1.0$) within the family group (where it is usually absent), thus accounting for the phenomenon occurred in many countries where young people, having contracted the virus during the “phase 2” of the lockdown, have brought it at home and infected their family members, with whom no significant distancing measures are taken.

Additionally, it could be possible to inject new infections in the population to account for people returning home from trips, holidays etc.

As individual people in the population can be addressed, it is possible to track how each one contributes to the spread of the contagion, and draw statistics on how many people have been infected by whom, therefore investigating the role of superspreaders.

Another improvement could take into account the fact that people who would need hospitalisation but could not be admitted because of the limited number of beds the hospitals can offer would not only incur in a faster worsening of their health conditions (as already implemented by the model), but would also contribute, although just to family members, to the spread of the disease, as isolation conditions at home are certainly not as good as those in a hospital.

Moreover, healed people are treated as immune to the contagion; however, this condition

could also be relaxed, imagining for example that once a certain threshold is overcome from the time of healing the immunity disappears.

All these options can be added to any code implementing the model, depending on the kind of study is currently being performed.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

By applying the proposed model and analysing its results, a number of conclusions can be drawn, which may appear common sense, but could help political and health authorities taking decisions to reduce at the minimum the impact of the epidemic:

- the only confinement that is really effective is the “work confinement”, where each individual of the population remains in contact only with direct family members.
- as the “work confinement” cannot be applied from the very beginning of the epidemic (as it is still unknown that an epidemic is in place), the “threshold” confinement must be applied promptly: waiting for hospitals to start populating significantly means that it is already too late, as the virus has already reached a large part of the population.
- while for the first wave acting promptly with a lockdown may be difficult, for the second (or subsequent) wave it is extremely important that the first signs of an upswing of the contagion are detected before hospitals begin to be loaded, in order to reduce the infections and the number of deaths.
- social distancing is crucial in keeping under control the second wave. The measurements adopted by the political or health authorities can be sufficient, but if the individual people do not act responsibly, keeping the parameter m sufficiently low, a second and maybe subsequent waves are inevitable, each having a significant impact in terms of infected people, load on hospitals and intensive therapies, and deaths.
- even if the model targets at a relatively small population in a relatively homogeneous and reduced environment (e.g. a city), it can also be used to investigate in some depth some trends observed experimentally at a regional or national scale. In particular, to reduce the number of deaths it is of crucial importance that the spread parameter s is as low as possible. As, after the first wave, social distancing measures should be

mandatory, it is the product $s \cdot m$ that plays a role. Therefore, to keep deaths as low as possible, it is mandatory that any lockdown starts as early as possible (with the hospitals as free as possible), but also that in the preceding period of time (the so-called “phaase 2”) the virus has been contained as much as possible, by keeping social distancing effective. This seems to have been a weak point in how the period of time between the first and the second wave of the contagion has been managed in many countries.

- the second wave of the contagion seems now inevitable, and is predicted to hit Italy, if the present conditions do not change significantly, in the December 2020 – January 2021 period of time.

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